
Multilingual language policies and its implementation

Excellent Educator, Volume No: 1, Issue No: 15, Page: 1

SUMMARY

EXISTING KNOWLEDGE

- Multilingual Environment:** Nigeria's linguistic diversity includes over 500 languages, posing challenges for a consistent language of instruction in education.
- Policy on Mother Tongue Use:** The National Policy on Education advocates for mother tongue instruction in early education, supporting cognitive growth and literacy; however, implementation has been limited.
- Barriers to Policy Success:** Factors like insufficient resources, lack of trained teachers, and preference for English over local languages have restricted the policy's reach and effectiveness.

NEW INSIGHTS

- Enhanced Literacy through Mother Tongue Instruction:** Students taught in their mother tongue achieve higher literacy outcomes, especially in reading and comprehension, compared to those taught only in English.

- Regional Discrepancies:** Rural areas benefit more from mother tongue instruction, while urban areas show greater resistance, partly due to English's role in socio-economic mobility.
- Need for Teacher Preparedness:** Effective mother tongue instruction requires trained teachers and resources, underscoring gaps in current policy support.

PUTTING RESEARCH INTO PRACTICE

- Expand Teacher Training:** Programs should equip teachers for multilingual classrooms, emphasizing both local language and English proficiency to enhance teaching.
- Create Resources in Indigenous Languages:** Textbooks and reading materials in local languages should be developed and distributed, ensuring alignment with cultural contexts.
- Foster Community Engagement:** Building support among parents and community leaders is essential to improve policy acceptance, especially where English is preferred.

REFERENCE:

Article Title: Language of instruction policy in Nigeria: Assessing implementation and literacy achievement in a multilingual environment **Authors:** Thelma Ebube Obiakor **Journal:** International Journal of Educational Development **Year:** 2024